

Stabilization of soil organic matter of palsa bogs as a response to climate change in Holocene

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Permafrost degradation in palsa bog ecosystems has a significant impact on global and regional carbon balances. The stability and biodegradability of soil organic matter (SOM) are crucial parameters for accurately assessing current and future carbon stocks. It is postulated that the extent of SOM stabilization in perennially frozen peatlands is currently underestimated. The mechanisms by which lignin biodegradation, subsequent demethylation, carboxylation and formation of condensed transformation products in the molecular composition of humic acids (HAs) occur under anaerobic conditions in peatland ecosystems remain essential and poorly understood in modern scientific research. It is also imperative to consider the vectors of stabilization of HAs beyond the mineral matrix (humus formation in oligotrophic conditions) and their resistance to fungal decomposition as key factors.

The ¹³C NMR and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) methods have been employed to elucidate the principal pathways of SOM stabilization in the peat deposit of palsa bogs in the European Arctic. Extremes of labile/condensed constituents and structural moieties have been found to be related to climatic and hydrological conditions during different periods of the Holocene. The highest content of condensed structures is observed in the peat layers formed during the Atlantic and Early Subboreal periods. The initial stage of SOM stabilization includes decomposition of plant residues, formation of (pro)humic substances (HSs) molecules from high-molecular-weight precursors, and primary transformation of HS molecules with degradation of the most labile fragments. Older HAs, which underwent intense degradation were enriched in the N,S-containing components as compared to surface layers. This is in turn accompanied by an overall decrease in the proportion of unoxidized aliphatic and carbohydrate fragments. A substantial proportion of highly condensed compounds were identified in HAs by HRMS. It was suggested that aromatic and condensed molecules contain long-chain substituents that contribute to the content of aliphatic carbon. The ratio of pentosans to hexosans in HAs is demonstrated to increase down the peat profile as a consequence of the redistribution of the dominant peat formers. The HA branching indices demonstrate a significant transformation of long-chain structures and an increase in the contribution of substituted aliphatic fragments in the HA structure. This allows for the reconstruction of past climates and prediction of the mechanisms of SOM stabilization under modern climatic changes.

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